

THE IMPORTANCE AND PROBLEMS OF GRAPHIC DESIGN TODAY

Branch Davranov Mirziyod

Student of TATU Samarkand

Indiaminov Ravshan Shukurovich

and the scientific leader

Email: ddddmirziyod@gmail.com

Phone number: +998996600451

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Anotation: this article is aimed at providing full-fledged information about the role of the field of graphic design today and its problems. And the article is aimed at solving problems that arise when working in this area and further revealing the field of knowledge.

Keywords: designer, Adobe, Photoshop, Illusiator, Corel draw, Prime pro, effects, SMM, Marketing

Graphic design is one of the directions of the field of design and serves to create, organize, design visual content in order to convey certain information to social groups. The main goal of graphic design is to identify problems and transform and correctly interpret them with creativity using innovative and digital tools.

Representatives of this industry, graphic designers, work on the interpretation of visual messages, their arrangement and presentation to the client. Design work can be based on a customer's request, a requirement linguistically defined either orally or in writing, meaning that a graphic designer converts a client's oral or written message into a graphic appearance.

Graphic design has different areas related to any visual communication according to the field of application. For example, it can be used in advertising strategies, or it can also be used in the aviation world or in space exploration. In this sense, graphic design in some countries is considered to be related only to the production of sketches and drawings, but this is incorrect, since visual communication is a small part of a huge number of types of areas in which it can be applied.

Graphic design, which appeared in antiquity and the Middle Ages, appeared in the West in the 19th century as a separate profession, and its evolution made it possible to grow more and more in the 20th century. Today, given the rapid and mass growth of information exchange, the demand for experienced designers is growing more than ever. And this is caused by the development of new technologies and the need to pay attention to human factors, in addition to the competence of engineers who develop them.

Basic elements of graphic design

Open element-along with images and graphic design elements, there are lines, shapes, textures, value, size and colors. Graphic designers for print and web pages use some or all of these elements to create effective designs. The goal is usually to attract the attention of the audience, and sometimes to encourage them to take certain actions.

- **Lines** - Lines is the most basic of the elements of design space. Linings can be flat, curved, thick, thin, firm and uneven. They are used when connecting two points, separate sections of the design, or when focusing the user's eye on the element. The soft line expresses feelings, that is, the line in which the Arrow ends forces the viewer's eye to look in a certain direction. The meanders between several elements guide the viewer from one element to the next.

- **Shapes** - the main geometric shapes are squares, circles and triangles. They are used as boxes or borders in design or as solid shapes for decorative purposes. Forms are also symbols, symbols and dingbats. Shapes add interest to the design.

- **Textures** - visual textures are created with a certain graphic technique to draw attention to the element of the space on the page or serve as a background in web design. It attracts attention, increasing the overall appearance of its texture. The type of texture can be added to the image and other elements.

- **Color** - color - a specific element that is used to attract attention and express feelings and moods. Red calls for strength, anger or passion, for example, Blue peace and security.

- **The value** of the value refers to how dark or lighter the design is. The value creates contrast and focus.

Volume-the size of an element's moment in a graphic design indicates its significance. Large volumes of information attract the attention of the viewer, showing the most important information.

Basic principles of graphic design

Graphic design elements combine with the principles of customization, balance, repetition, intimacy, contrast, and space to create effective page compositions.

The principles of graphic design reflect the ways in which graphic designers can combine whole elements one by one. Designers draw the viewer's attention to an important element by placing an important element where the eye naturally falls. Other classic design principles include:

- **Balance** - The best graphic designs are visually appealing. About the center visually using symmetrical, asymmetrical or lamellar symmetry. Provides balance. In symmetric equilibrium, the page layout is the same on both sides in

weight, shape, lines and other elements. Asymmetric equilibrium occurs when the two sides of a website are not the same, but they have similar elements. Elements of Radial symmetry are arranged in a circular pattern. Although popular in print, radial symmetry is not very prominent on websites because circular layout is difficult. Note: Sometimes, a graphic designer usually produces an unstable design, trying to focus attention on a single element.

▪ **Alignment** - Alignment refers to the placement of design elements along the top, bottom, center or sides of the elements. Aligned elements do not have to be of the same type. They are often located on the left side of the layout. Photos of different sizes are displayed as units when matched above or below.

▪ **Repetition** - repetition refines the characteristics of similar elements. Repetition can also create a rhythm in the design. Interesting ideas of the same color, type and size for a complete unit.

▪ **Proximity** - intimacy maintains the relationship between what the moment passes together. It is not necessary to place the elements close to each other, but they are visually appealing. Must be associated with.

▪ **Contrast** - contrast occurs with the reciprocal agreement of elements in which the space is small or black, for example, and has opposition to the resistance. The use of contrast can emphasize important elements of the design. Contrast is easily achieved with color, but it can also appear with textures, types and graphic elements.

Space - space is part of the design of the space left empty. In it, the design also includes space deliberately placed, as well as spaces between other elements, which are usually called passive space. The design of the space in the design adds attention to one area, since it attracts the eye to the composition of the non-empty design. In graphic design, both the positive and negative field should be considered.

Along with the development of modern technologies, the Marketing industry is rapidly developing. It is difficult to imagine the Marketing industry without SMM.

Social Media Marketing [SMM] is an English – language social media marketing that is considered a form of Internet Marketing. Its main goal is to attract customers from social networks to your products and services. I don't think we have to discuss how big social media is. This network evolved even faster than the internet itself.

When working in this area, I believe that the following should and should be trusted.

1. The given design should be understandable,clear.
2. Supply and demand should be summarized.
3. The goal is to create a Compania or client work within the required framework.

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Mock up-are models used for the purpose of showing how further exposure of images is used in the field of self.

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The app is an app that can handle all of the effects and actions to be done on objects that sum up the most up-to-date in **Photoshop** performance.

The application that works with vector graphics is the Illusiator.Loga brand and is an app that creates all of the images and disains used for walls or websites.

You can find all mock up and official AI photos through the PINTEREST app.

To summarize from this article, let's say become a modern professional and start your own personal business or business using the current technologies efficiently and do not stop getting ahead to the future. IT is considered the profession of keljak through which create apps and games that the world recognizes and hope that you will be the person who will make our homeland known to the world.

References:

1. Graphic design-Wikipedia (The Free Encyclopedia yandexwebcache.net)
2. Elements and principles of graphic design (eyewated.com)
3. Design brand.Alina Wheeler.2017
4. Phaidon.Zhe chao.Phaidon print 2013.
- 5.<https://kitobxon.com/oz/kitob/arhitektura-va-dizayn-grafikasi?ysclid=lqum19vmhv264022015>

